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Connecting the world with Internet of Things

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ABSTRACT

Connecting the world sounds like a very challenging undertaking when it comes to gathering information, analysing and distributing data. *Internet of Things* is the concept of connecting any device to the internet while internetworking with devices. Possibilities for applications of *Internet of Things* are numerous to connect multiple systems while using the shared data for industrial and economic purposes or for empowering citizens and communities, among others. At Eindhoven University of Technology (the Netherlands) there are courses that aim at educating engineers to use applications for industrial purposes, but also for society and business solutions. The second year design-based learning sophomore course *Internet of Things* focuses on teaching students to solve open-ended problems both in industry or in hospital settings. . In this paper, we present the set-up of the *Internet of Things* project in which students explore different indoor localization scenarios. We explain as well the rationale for the selected approach to teach this *Internet of Things* project. In addition, we give an overview of the main characteristics which feature the project, and we describe some expected benefits for the students.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development; Skills and Engineering Education; Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

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INTRODUCTION

Imaging a connected world is easy although the potential of the *Internet of things* (IoT) application is still to discover. Possibilities for applications are manifold to connect multiple systems while using the shared data for industrial and economic purposes or for empowering citizens and communities, among others. IoT is more than just a buzzer word that can be applied to a wide range of devices, technologies and situations. IoT is the concept of connecting any device to the internet while internetworking with, for instance, cellphones, connected vehicles, wearable devices or buildings by the use of sensors, actuators, and software of network connections [1].

At the Electrical Engineering (EE) department at the Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) the theme of IoT is starting to boom up. The rationale to integrate IoT in the EE curriculum is driven by the fact that IoT is quickly gaining an industrial foothold in the Netherlands and internationally. In addition, engineers with IoT knowledge and skills are already required by many companies. Furthermore, while a need for this expertise is evident, there are no hands-on specific courses or lab environments at the TU/e where students can be exposed to the IoT experience. The motivation for this project is to develop an IoT hands-on project within the EE curriculum in order to facilitate students gaining practical skills.

In this paper, we give first an overview of the IoT project assignment within the EE study program. Secondly, we also provide an outline of the multidisciplinary components of this project to develop new insights into possible business applications. Finally, we address the expected benefits of this pilot project.

1 THE CONTEXT OF *INTERNET OF THINGS*

1.1 The rationale for the development of a IoT project in *FLUX*

Internet of Things (IoT) is the internetworking of physical devices, vehicles, buildings and other items. IoT enable devices including electronics, software, sensors, actuators, and network connectivity modules in order to collect and exchange data. IoT is becoming a growing market making a stand in the industrial world in the Netherlands and internationally.

At the TU/e (the Netherlands) there are courses at the Computer Science and Industrial Engineering departments devoted to teach students the technological aspects of IoT, i.e., architectures, device classes, protocols, application patterns and application examples, among others. In addition, courses also focus on developing business models and business cases on the products students make. However, the industry needs engineers with hands-on skills able to innovate and implement applications to match customer value needs and businesses.

The second year design-based learning sophomore project course *Internet of Things* at the Electrical Engineering (EE) department aims at teaching students to learn to use the applications of IoT around gravel/net, the expandable wireless IoT network of 50 nodes deployed inside of the EE department, the ultra-modern and recently-constructed building '*FLUX*' (See Figure 1). Moreover, our purpose for the development of this hands-on project is to make possible to run new applications, hosting various sensors and other hardware. This network is the result of several past

and ongoing research programs. However it is not yet big and mature enough to be used for educational purposes. It should scale, in principal, to 180-200 nodes and become robust and easy to use allowing both teachers and students to focus on learning objectives rather than on solving technical issues.

Within this project, students learn how to design wireless links (including basic concepts of antenna design), and to optimize end-to-end latency over an IoT network. Likewise, students become familiar with different wireless protocols while exploring the relation between signal noise ration and channel capacity, the design of low energy systems by the use of algorithms of localization.

The project has a multidisciplinary character as elements of architectures from the computer science field and the economic values from the business world are integrated in the cases of the students to complement the electrical engineering knowledge that students will gain throughout the implementation. In addition, students from other departments, mainly Computer Science and Innovation Sciences, work together with Electrical Engineering in teams.

1.2 The description of the IoT project and the use cases

The end purpose of the IoT project assignment is to have students to solve open-ended and realistic use cases as they would be tackling complex problems of a real world scenarios. The assignment is based on tracing people in a factory, or patients in a hospital, or expensive equipment in the university. All assignments have a common denominator, i.e. indoor localization functionality. However, each of these cases has different requirements. On the one hand, in an industrial floor with robots and humans, safety critical situations picked by sensors have to immediately be notified to the control room or robots in the vicinity. On the other hand, patients in a hospital need to be tracked either in a waiting room or through the thick walls of a surgery room. The students are challenged to select a scenario in which both a tracking system as well as designing a solution for it is needed.

Given a selected scenario (i.e. industrial floor or hospital setting) the students need to define the functional and non-functional requirements in order to prioritize them together with the stakeholders and product owners. The sort-listing of these requirements will guide the student to the design of the architecture and the integration of the different technologies at market level. That is why the students will hold several presentations to fine tune the prototypes according to the market demands. The stakeholders and product owners will be present to these presentations in order to give their feedback as soon as possible, enabling students to readjust prototypes in iterations. It is therefore an evolving design trying to continuously address exactly the customer demands.

The system under design is split into both hardware and software components. Each human to be tracked should be equipped with a small low-power device. In reality, it is that device the whole IoT system is tracking; for clarity, we call this device mobile. The system consists of several fixed small devices deployed in various spots in a building (e.g. ceiling, walls, windows, floor, tables etc). Through different communication techniques the fixed devices “see” the mobile ones and through triangulation they are capable of determining their exact position. There are multitude dimensions to be considered when designing such a system. Accuracy of localization, number of fixed

devices, data collection for centralized management, and lifetime of battery powered devices to name a few. These are questions inherent to the assignment of the students. Answering those questions, always in view of the priorities of stakeholders, will help the students short-list the wireless technologies (ultra-wide band or ultrasonic), the hardware (low-power or resource-full) and software architecture (centralized, hybrid, decentralized) to be used.

Together with this design process, the students will be integrating the chosen combination of technologies and will be testing their choices. It is via reading, trial-and-error and consulting with experts and stakeholders that they will be learning concluding to the best product design. The validation of their project output will be done on a real IoT testbed (i.e. gravel/net) deployed in the department of Electrical Engineering, at the TU/e. The testbed counts for 150 fixed devices and around 30 mobile ones. All the devices are extendible with the combination of technologies students will integrate. The testbed is able to collect monitoring information and let the student download performance data of their experiments. Yet, it is up to the students to design their experiments and applications running on top. An illustration of gravel/net is given in Fig. 1, 2, and 3². For instance, in safety critical use cases (factory) gravel/net will be able to inform the students of the delay of an alarm trigger from sensors in the field all the way to the control room of the factory. Symmetrically, gravel/net will notify the students when a human stopped being traceable either because left e.g. the hospital or got in a surgery room. It is up to the students to assess whether that was a desired performance or reaction to an event.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

² All images in figures 1–5 belong to the author George Exarchakos (g.exarchakos@tue.nl)

Fig. 3

Moreover, for industrial applications with coordination with robots, these have to be coordinated precisely one product to the other. When it goes about robots issues such as people and safety or alarm are key important elements. At the end of the course, the students will demonstrate that their solution can indeed solve the challenge taking into consideration specifications such as speed and efficient use of energy.

1.3 The IoT assignment

The objectives of this DBL IoT project are:

- To optimized wireless links (including basic concepts of antenna design)
- To optimize end-to-end latency over an IoT network
- To get familiar with different wireless protocols
- To create and analyse relations between signal noise ratio and channel capacity
- To design for low energy systems
- To apply algorithms of localization
- To conduct analysis of large data sets
- To develop new insights into possible business application of the IoT case

The motivation behind this project course is to introduce students in the world of the *Internet of Things* by applying technology, architecture and business models by tracing people and objects in indoor localization functionally assignments.

Next to the technical challenges also the business aspects of the project will be explored within the students' groups. Students make use of a business case and models to notify in the production line. The added element of including business models and cases is to have students to get involved in real live assignments in which they have to gather information on crowd sensing applications to be able to understand how crowd works, for instance, for safety and business purposes while deploying the necessary application. The key element is that students see the product development part of such as real-life case as they may work in a small company with similar challenges.

The structure of the project consists of seven weeks and eight contact hours per week in which students carry out the project activities. Besides an introductory meeting on the *Internet of Things* assignments, students get two support lectures on the two main multidisciplinary topics in this project, i.e. architectures, and business models and cases. These support lectures are given by lecturers from the Computer Science and Innovation Sciences departments. In addition, the Electrical Engineering lecturers are also involved in the direct supervision of the teachers.

Following the educational principles of problem-based and project-based learning, students work in teams together throughout seven weeks. The groups are guided by a supervisor or project leaders. These are older bachelor or master students with broad knowledge on the *Internet of Things* as they have been involved in the construction of the network. The groups are made out up to 6 students and the tasks are divided among them.

The follow-up of the project activities and interim products is based on mid-term presentations in which students report about the progress of the project, main obstacles but also the challenges ahead and how these will be solved. In these mid-term presentations the interim products and prototypes, are assessed. Students receive feedback from the experts on how to make improvements including from a company in charge of providing proof-of-concept input. The presentations and final report are assessed against quality of final products.

2 INSTRUCTIONAL DESIGN IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

2.1 The Design-based learning approach of the *Internet of Things* project

Design-based learning (DBL) is an active learning teaching method similar to Problem-based learning [4] and Project-based learning [5] engaging students in solving real-life design problems while reflecting on the design and learning process [6]. DBL was introduced at the TU/e in 1997 as an educational approach for engineering education. The unique element of DBL is that it is grounded in the *process of inquiry and reasoning towards generating innovative artifacts, systems and solutions* [7]. DBL emphasizes the engineering design process resembling authentic engineering settings in which students make decisions during the design cognitive thinking processes as they go through iterations in generating specifications, making predictions, experiencing and creating solutions, testing and communicating [7].

Resembling the DBL model from empirical literature, we have included the features of DBL [8], i.e., *open-ended, hands-on, authentic and multidisciplinary* aspects in the instructional design of the *Internet of Things* second year bachelor project. The *open-ended* character of the project is featured by the fact that students get a general description of the cases to explore from different perspectives. As an instance, students are to trace people in buildings, workers in a factory, patients in a hospital or just lab equipment. Besides the description of the use case with incomplete information and some specifications expected in the final systems, students' teams are to experiment iteratively with different architectures to be able to choose the appropriate one that matches the technology selected for the design. Within this experiencing phase and following the common engineering design process, students make a thorough out analysis of the use cases and requirements and choose some criteria to select the proper architecture. In addition, students' teams analyse the business aspects and make priorities of the requirements and features of the system to be developed.

As in the engineering design cycle, students formulate own design plan, and seek for alternatives in the design of the architecture and integration of existing architectures and communication technologies. In the integration process, the selection and assembly of the required hardware, installation of software, modules and libraries, etc., should be included. The next steps in the design process are to test iteratively the prototypes and experiencing repeatedly various architectures in order to design a minimum viable product, i.e. a prototype which is not the final product. The design and testing phases should be in iterations so that students can expand the design with different features of each specific case. A relevant element within the design process is the feedback to support the construction of a viable product so that this can be sold and become profitable. These project assignments provide students the opportunity to experience a typical production development process from the organization of working

from a traditional waterfall production and design work into a much more *Agile* type of work consisting of short iterations allowing companies to realise new products in short time.

The fact that the assignments are embedded in *real life* industry tasks make the cases more *authentic* resembling jobs students might get in companies. The teaching staff from the Computer Science and Industrial Engineering departments will be also providing feedback as part of the customers' roles they will be playing. Moreover, the *hands-on* component of this project is actually inserted in the generation of knowledge from each iteration in the design process which is afterwards applied in a new iteration producing new information on the prototype to make.

In this *hands-on* project students are asked to work in *multi-disciplinary* groups to address a challenge concerning how a large pool of IoT devices connected to form an intelligent network can be used to solve practical engineering problems relating to emerging applications such as autonomous driving and in building navigation and localization. The rationale for multidisciplinary lies in that students from the different three departments, i.e. Electrical Engineering, Computer Science, and Industrial Engineering will be working together and share expertise from multiple domains i.e. design, integration-implementation, testing-deployment and business models. As a matter of fact the involvement of Computer Science in this project is related to the software architectures of a system, of Electrical Engineering to the hardware assembly and of Industrial Engineering to the value proposition and the business models.

3 INNOVATION SPACE AND THE ENGINEERS FOR THE FUTURE

The *Internet of Things* project is a pilot which has potential to expand and link with the newly initiated concept of Innovation Space at the TU/e. Since 2016 the idea of the TU/e Innovation Space (still under construction) is built upon the rationale to have students work on hands-on engineering assignments in multidisciplinary teams while dealing with challenging and *complex societal and industrial challenges, create prototypes and develop innovations in collaboration with researchers, businesses and other stakeholders...*[2]. The added value of this initiative is the strong scientific collaboration that the TU/e has with the surrounding industry, with researchers and businesses.

The concept of Innovation Space does not stand alone in the world. Looking at other initiatives overseas, for instance, the Design Factory at the Finnish Aalto University, this has been an inspiring example to adjust that model into the TU/e pattern. The experience of *Design factory* illustrates and leads the TU/e project to make possible and give form to a space in which the physical and mental working environment for product developers and researchers come together to encourage and to enable fruitful interaction between students, researchers, and professional practitioners. Following the already 10-year old Finnish model, the TU/e innovation space provides a setting to inspire teaching staff and students for which lectures and workshops are organized. In addition, the fact that the Innovation Space provides a scenario for the implementation of multidisciplinary engineering projects encourages the engineering thinking of creating prototypes and transforming those into products, services for the society in order to stimulate businesses. Compared to other models, the TU/e innovation space specific character lies on encouraging the cross-fertilization between departments as well as the cooperation with the business community. The operationalization of such

an ambitious undertaking is actually a step ahead in realizing the vision of the TU/e to educate the Engineers for the Future [3].

4 DISCUSSION

The *Internet of Things* project is a pilot project that has been developed to introduce students in the world of communication technology and to learn them the application of technology, architecture and business models by tracing people and objects through indoor localization functionally assignments. The added value of this project is that is a pioneering course within the Eindhoven University of Technology as it is devoted to promote *hands-on* application of a connected world rather than in a lecture-type course. The relevance of this project is therefore twofold: first of all, the IoT project is aiming at promoting practical applications of content; secondly, the project aims at integrating different disciplines as a realistic scenario of what the engineers for the future will be dealing with in the industry in order to stimulate multidisciplinary projects.

It becomes difficult at this stage to sharply identify the benefits and students' gains of this project as it is now in a pilot phase. We foresee however some advantages and effects for students. First of all, the rationale for this project is based on integrating continuous iterations in the design process emulating the *Agile* method. By doing so, we expect higher quality of product design, in terms of accuracy of localization, measurements of distance, or in the optimization levels of the wireless network, among other performance items of the devices. Furthermore, the fact that students can choose different scenarios and perspectives to approach the problem solution will require creativity to combine technologies and architectures. We expect therefore new eye openers in the models students will design. A thorough out evaluation of results after the implementation of this pilot project will allow us to analyse students' gains in this IoT project.

The future challenges of this project will be to include elements of value for money in the design review in order to fine-tune the assignments and students' products according to the clients. In order to embrace the value for money component it will be necessary to make the project sustainable and gain financial support to be able to buy sensors, actuators and missing parts upon which students will make choices based on the technology and architectures they are planning to use. The need to link with the industry and with Innovation Space university project becomes also relevant.

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REFERENCES

- [1] *The Internet of things: An overview. Understanding the issues and challenges of a more connected world.* (2015). Internet Society.
https://www.internetsociety.org/sites/default/files/ISOC-IoT-Overview-20151014_0.pdf
- [2] www.tue.nl
- [3] Meijers, A. and den Brok, P., (2013), Engineers for the future: an essay on education at TU/e in 2030, Eindhoven University of Technology.
- [4] Kolmos, A., De Graaff, E., & Du, X. (2009). Diversity of PBL—PBL learning principles and models. In D. Xiangyun, E. de Graaff, & A. Kolmos (Eds.), *Research on PBL practice in engineering education*, Rotterdam: Sense Publishers. pp. 9–21.
- [5] Dym, C. L., Agogino, A. M., Eris, O., Frey, D. D., & Leifer, L. J. (2005). Engineering design thinking, teaching, and learning. *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 94, No.1, pp. 103–120.
- [6] Doppelt, Y., Mehalik, M. M., Schunn, C. D., Silk, E., & Krysinski, D. (2008). Engagement and achievements: A case study of design-based learning in a science context. *Journal of Technology Education*, Vol. 19, No. 2, pp. 22–39.
- [7] Mehalik, M. M., Doppelt, Y., & Schunn, C. D. (2008). Middle-school science through design-based learning versus scripted inquiry: Better overall science concept learning and equity gap reduction. *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 97, No. 1, pp. 71–85.
- [8] Gómez Puente, S.M., Eijck, van, M.W. & Jochems, W.M.G. (2013). A sampled literature review of design-based learning approaches: a search for key characteristics. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 23(3), pp. 717-732.